

How organizations can automate HCI collaboration with artificial intelligent agents?

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

The increasing rise of automation in technology operations demonstrate a natural evolution of human assisted tools such as artificially programmed personal agents who will soon become complementary with our day to day job tasks. Similarly, we rely nowadays mostly on computers and can hardly imagine how difficult it would be to generate a report and share it with hundreds of team members in seconds without a computer.

We should then question how to scale human-computer interaction to increase team collaboration when using conversational virtual agents? And how to prepare organizations manage and adopt such artificial intelligence technologies to not reduce work efficiency within team collaboration?

2. Aim

To answer these questions, the main objective of this research is to investigate how humans and conversational intelligent machines can better collaborate based on search recommendation patterns which are matched with different parties instead of automated bidirectional responses.

3. Material and methods

With the use of predictive index learning indicators such as The Predictive Index Cognitive Assessment TestTM, organizations can easily assess an individual's ability to learn and grasp new concepts of work. Thus, we will be testing a framework applied on both humans and Chatbots interactions to validate the level of a user beforehand, it will help us determine how the flow of information should be distributed accordingly for better adoption and use within a coaching platform "Mastrbrain".

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4. Results

We are building this empirical model to validate our hypothesis, by first programming a fully operational Chatbot who will be able to learn then communicate appropriate information requested by its peers on the training platform “Mastrbrain”. Then, in a second phase we will present how we teach our Chatbot to interpret cognitive levels of individuals with whom he has interactions on same topics discussed initially without bias and compare the result patterns.

5. Conclusions

According to the results of this study, we will be presenting a list of recommendations that will help organizations build an automated collaborative interaction process between a human and a virtual artificial agent.

6. Keywords

Human-Computer Interaction (HCI); Chatbot; Cobot; Artificial Intelligence; Machine Learning; Collaborative intelligence; MastrBrain; Université de Sherbrooke.

Author biography

Karim N. Osmane Karim N. Osmane is a research scientist and doctoral candidate at Université de Sherbrooke since 2013. He has completed his MBA in 2011 at Virginia International University and earned a certificate diploma in Innovation & Strategy from Harvard University and Developing a Leading-Edge Operations Strategy from MIT School of Management.

Karim has worked in software development and quality assurance in various industries including (IVR, Chatbots, Contact Centers) in both USA and Canada. He is now a QA Automation Lead Manager at Desjardins and co-founder of Mastrbrain; a coaching platform based in Montreal while completing his research studies in business administration.